

Revolutionizing Sterile Sample Culturing: Cost-Effective Centrifugation Techniques for Research in Resource-Constrained Settings

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Abstract

Introduction: The yield (culture positive rate) of sterile body fluids in patients was found to be less than 50%. It has been demonstrated that centrifuging body fluid before culturing increases yield. Using concentrated bacterial samples to enhance culture growth is a more effective alternative. We sought to determine whether sterile fluid culture yield was increased by centrifugation. **Methods:** Patients whose body fluids were received in sufficient quantity in the microbiology lab were enrolled. Sterile body fluids culture was carried out after centrifugation and by routine conventional inoculation method which was taken as a reference method. **Results:** 250 samples were included in the study over six months. Of the 250 samples, 15 came positive by the conventional method and 37 came positive by centrifugation technique. Comparisons were made between the turnaround times for the two methods. However, the centrifugation approach immediately produced positive Gram stain results for 19 samples ($p = 0.03$) while the reference method only produced three positive results. When compared to using the reference technique, the centrifugation method achieved bacterial identification and sensitivity on average more quickly ($p = 0.00001$). **Conclusion:** The centrifugation technique was successful in producing the desired outcomes and may be used in the future with such precious samples. The centrifugation technique may shorten the turnaround time for culture reports, improving the management of infectious disorders.

Introduction

Ascitic, pleural, synovial, cerebral fluid, aqueous humour, bile, and other body fluid are typically sterile but can become infected by bacteria. It is believed that even the presence of a single organism in these sites is important, which could lead to an increase in morbidity and mortality [1]. Invasive procedures used for diagnostic or therapeutic purposes raise the risk of infection. Because there are fewer organisms present in the specimen, conventional microbiologists find it difficult to isolate microbes from these sites. Many methods were explored to produce a positive yield in the culture to overcome this challenge. The most popular technique used by the majority of laboratories

is centrifugation of the large number of samples and the preparation of sediments for cultivation. Other research has demonstrated that when compared to traditional approaches, automated technologies are superior. We must look into less expensive ways that might boost the yield of positive in the body fluid culture because automated cultures are an expensive study for many microbiological labs and patients, at least in developing countries, due to the expensive equipment and high cost.

The final report can take at least two days to obtain using conventional procedures. Empirical antibiotics are immediately recommended for typical pathogen coverage while treating infectious diseases in people,

More Information

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and the most efficient agents are then changed based on the results of the treatment. The physical and chemical properties of the culture media affect how quickly bacteria grow. The quantity of bacteria introduced to the culture media can also have an impact on how quickly bacteria grow. The rate of bacterial growth can be accelerated to boost this by utilising concentrated sample[2]. The conventional method and the centrifuging technique are used as the reference method in our analysis. The two methods turnaround times for the culture findings were also analyzed.

Materials and Methods

Between October 2019 and March 2020, this investigation was carried out in the microbiology department at VMCM and Safdarjung Medical College. 250 sterile body fluid samples from various locations, including the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), pleural fluid, and ascitic fluid, were collected in total. These samples were subjected to culture using the standard conventional method (direct inoculation and automated BacTAlert 3D system), as well as multiple centrifugations. Direct inoculation method was taken as gold standard method. Media used for the both techniques were 5% sheep blood agar, Chocolate agar, MacConkey agar. In the conventional methods the sample were directly inoculated in to the culture medium and direct gram stain was prepared from the samples. For centrifugation, 10 – 15 ml of the sterile body fluid was taken in a sterile falcon tubes and sample was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes for minimum of three times. After which the supernatant fluid was discarded and sediment was inoculated onto 5 % sheep blood agar which is a enriched media, MacConkey agar which is a differential media and Chocolate agar is used for the growth of fastidious organism. All the plates were incubated for 18-24 hour at 37°C . Gram staining was done from the specimen both before and after centrifugation, and the results

were noted. The culture plates that had no growth after 24 and 48 hours were recorded as having no growth, and the plates that had growth were processed further in accordance with CLSI criteria to identify the bacterium and the pattern of antibiotic susceptibility. Each technique's time to positivity was noted. As soon as bacteria were discovered and the results of antibiotic susceptibility tests became available, the findings from both methods were reported. For every sample and method, the report times were recorded. After two days of culture, the results were labelled as "culture negative" since the BACTEC culture system was unable to find any bacterial signals in the culture bottles. The variables from the two groups were compared using the chi-square test. The Mann-Whitney test was used when data were presented as the median (interquartile range). Statistical significance was defined as a p-value of 0.05 or lower.

Results

250 samples were processed using the automated, centrifugation, and conventional method; the frequencies of positive cultures in each case were 15, 25, and 37 respectively. Table 1 illustrates the specimen's division into parts and its growth. All the cultures that showed positive in conventional method were also positive in automated and centrifugation method with the growth of the same organism. Both isolates antibiotic susceptibility patterns were comparable, suggesting that they were likely from the same strain. In the centrifugation method, exhibited good amount of positivity was noted in pleural fluid and ascitic fluid whereas automated methods yield better positivity in Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). There was only 4(3.44%) culture positivity in ascitic fluid by conventional method but 12(13.7%) showed positive by centrifugation method. The result showed significantly enhanced culture positivity overall with a p value of 0.005.

Table 1: Samples Distribution and Culture Growth in Different Methods

Samples	Total	Conventional method		Automated method		Centrifugation method		p-value
		Growth	No growth	Growth	No growth	Growth	No growth	
Ascites fluid	126	04	122	08	118	12	116	0.195
CSF	49	08	41	11	38	16	33	0.118
Pleural fluid	75	03	72	06	69	09	66	0.159
Total	250	15	235	25	225	37	213	0.0051

Table 2: Distribution of Organisms by Different Method

Isolates	Pleural fluid			Ascitic fluid			CSF		
	Conv	Auto	Centri	Conv	Auto	Centri	Conv	Auto	Centri
<i>Acinetobacter spp.</i>	1	1	2	0	1	1	2	2	3
<i>Enterococcus spp.</i>	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1

<i>Klebsiella spp.</i>	0	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	3
<i>Enterobacter spp.</i>	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	1	2
<i>E. coli</i>	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
CoNs	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	2	2

Table 3: Comparison with reference method

Reference	Centrifugation	Reference	P value
Gram stain report pathogens	19	3	0.0381
Bacteria identification time (hours)	16-36(IQR=9.25)	20-40(IQR=15)	<0.00001
Sensitivity report time (hours)	30-55(IQR=21)	38-96(IQR=34)	<0.00001

The culture result report times of the two different methods. Only 3 pathogens were found by routine Gram staining in pre-culture samples in the reference group. However, Gram staining identified pathogens in 19 samples after the centrifuging but before streaking the samples on agar plates for subsequent culture ($p = 0.03$). The lengths of times needed for pathogens to be identified or for antibiotic susceptibility test results to be available were significantly shorter for the Centrifugation method compared with the reference method ($p < 0.00001$).

The results of the centrifugation procedure were not used to direct our treatment because this was a study on diagnostic accuracy. The centrifugation technique may be able to identify bacteria more quickly. The centrifugation procedure resulted in a reduced culture report time (including bacterial identification and antibiotic-sensitivity report, see Table 3). It implied that patients with infections caused by methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) could have received vancomycin earlier. Similarly, gentamicin may have been stopped earlier in cases of infection caused by Gram-negative bacteria.

Discussion

Because of the low load of the organism, the organism's phagocytosis, or the organism's trap in organic substances, the problem of retrieving the organism from body fluids is exceedingly challenging. There are many ways to lyse the cell to release the organism and damage the organic contents, which increases the likelihood of successfully cultivating these specimens. Taylor et al [3] observed that sonication of the sample before culturing on saponin containing media resulted in increased positivity. In our study comparing with the conventional technique which yielded 6% positivity, the centrifugation technique resulted in 15% of positivity. Many studies have demonstrated very significant positivity (89%) by lysis centrifugation of blood specimen [4,5]. Daur et al [6] had compared isolation of organism from body fluids from different site by both conventional and enrichment culture technique and found 9.7% of specimens showed positive with conventional method and 23.1% with enriched broth

culture technique, using BacT/Alert blood culture bottle. In our study we also encountered a significant number of positivity 15% using BacT/Alert blood culture bottle. Bourbeau et al [7] performed a study with sterile body fluid samples other than blood by culturing routine as well as BacT/Alert standard aerobic anaerobic bottles and BacT/Alert FAN anaerobic bottles and reported recovery of organisms in 82%, 96% and 81% respectively standard bottles, FAN bottles and routine cultures. We in our study used automated and centrifugation method to look for enhanced culture positivity. As compared to other studies which got a significant recovery of gram positive organisms, our study reported isolation of gram negative organisms predominately by centrifugation method and also we have not done isolation of anaerobic organisms. Elston et al [8] reported 94% of culture positivity by isolator detection system in comparing with 64% positivity by large volume centrifugation method. They did their study with 155 body fluid samples other than blood, CSF and Urine. So, in set up which cannot afford for expensive automated culture system, centrifugation method can be cheapest and efficient to retrieve culture positivity.

We could respond earlier and prescribe the appropriate antibiotics treatment to patient if results were obtained faster with the centrifugation method. We could also avoid using a nephrotoxic aminoglycoside in Gram-positive infections and prescribe vancomycin earlier in MRSA infections. Theoretically, the centrifugation method could reduce medical costs and duration of hospital stay for many patients.

Limitations

We had to repeatedly expose samples to air, which might have prevented the growth of any anaerobic bacteria. The reference method did not yield any anaerobic bacteria identification, and neither did the centrifugation approach yield any anaerobic bacterium searches. So, it's unclear if anaerobic bacteria will be a problem. The current study is constrained by the limited sample size.

Conclusion

We draw the conclusion that sample processing involving repeated centrifugation can concentrate bacteria and reduce the time it takes to produce culture reports. It is a cheap and safe procedure. According to the results of our study, this strategy could help patients by reducing the time it takes to confirm an illness. This would be advantageous for patients' health and financial well-being. The clinical advantages of this strategy will need to be demonstrated in a prospective randomised control study that uses the results of the centrifugation method to direct antibiotic treatment.

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